

NODES

Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE N 2 – Title GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D5.1

Version history

No.	Date	Details	Author(s)
1	03/10/2023		Silvia Fraterrigo Garofalo Debora Fino

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

A) Main objectives achieved

The main objectives of this RM are the definition and selection of the technological solutions available to be tested at the industrial level for CO₂ capture and conversion and the expected results from the activities foreseen in this RM will lead, through a comparison between the different technologies at the level of applied research, to the definition of the best technologies available in this sector.

During this first 10 month of project the task 5.1 has been completed (more details from page 8 to page 22) and in particular the main results achieved are:

- The existing literature was examined to assess the current state of the art in CO₂ capture materials.
- A CO₂ capture material was chosen to synthesize, characterize and test.
- The existing literature was examined to assess the current state of the art in CO₂ conversion through chemical, photochemical, electrochemical, and biochemical processes.
- The technologies and materials to be tested for the chemical, photochemical, electrochemical, and biochemical conversion of CO₂ into high-value-added molecules have been selected.
- The typical composition of gas emissions from a power plant was determined to select the gaseous mixtures for conducting CO₂ capture and conversion tests..
- Milestone 5.1 has been achieved (more details at page 24).

B) Research Module n° 5

CO₂ capture and conversion platform: biochemical, chemo-catalytic and electrochemical conversion processes

RM5 will deal with Carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions. CO₂ is one of the main responsible of the rapid rise in global temperature. The RM5 plans to identify a suitable technology for the capture and conversion of CO₂ for industrial application in a steady state. Mineral capture of CO₂ from industrial/engines emissions will be applied and evaluated in synergy with the other carbon capture methods with a view to providing a diverse portfolio of solutions to the carbon dioxide rise in the atmosphere. Carbon capture and storage will complete the previous approaches to the reduction of the impact of urban and industrial waste by acting on the gaseous waste from

anthropic activities. The RM5 also aims to develop a suitable technology for the subsequent conversion of trapped CO₂ for the synthesis of methanol and other high-value molecules through multiple synthetic bio-chemical, chemical and electrochemical strategies. The processes will be optimized first on a laboratory scale and subsequently validated on a pilot scale.

List of Deliverables

Table - List of Deliverables

N°	OUTPUTS/DELIVERABLE NAME	TYPE *	SHORT DESCRIPTION	LEAD PARTICIPANT	DISSEMINATION LEVEL **	DUE DATE
5.1	Data acquisition and material characterization	R	Collection of data, Characterization of the composition of gases at the emittee for the identification of the specifications required for CO ₂ capture and conversion, selection of the experimental set-ups.	POLITO	PU	10
5.2.1	Development and	R	Synthesis,	POLITO-	PU	20

	optimization of materials and systems for CO ₂ capture.		characterization and tests on adsorption materials	UNITO		
5.2.2	CO ₂ Conversion by thermochemistry.	R	Tests, evaluation of material conversion capacity and products characterization	POLITO	PU	30
5.2.3	CO ₂ Conversion by electrochemistry	R	Tests, evaluation of material conversion capacity and product characterization	POLITO	PU	30
5.2.4	Biochemical conversion of CO ₂	R	Optimization of the growth process and products characterization	POLITO	PU	30
5.3	Products application	R	Investigation of market trends and application of products	POLITO	PU	32
5.4	Environmental constraints	R	Comparison between the three processes of CO ₂ being equal from an environmental sustainability point of view	POLITO	PU	32

List of Milestones

Table - List of Project Milestones

MILESTONE NUMBER	MILESTONE NAME	RELATED WORK MODULES	DUE DATE (MONTH)	MEANS OF VERIFICATION
M5.1	CO ₂ capture and conversion materials	5	10	At least one material to be tested for each conversion process and also microorganism for the

				biochemical process will be selected.
M5.2	CO ₂ capture and conversion processes	5	32	The best process will be identified among those investigated from a technical, economic and environmental point of view.

C) General description of the Deliverable D1.1

Data acquisition and material characterization

T.5.1.1. Collection of data, identification of the specifications required for CO₂ capture and conversion, selection of the experimental set-ups.

Polito and UNITO will collect the literature and patent data to learn about the state of the art on CO₂ capture and conversion in the four areas: biochemical, chemical, electrochemical and mineral sequestration. In particular, Polito will investigate the pressure and temperature characteristics of the gas flows to be treated, the average composition and the flow rates for the CO₂ capture will be identified and shared with the partnership. Polito will deal with the choice of the catalyst to be synthesized and tested for CO₂ capture in Task 5.2. Polito will deal with the choice of the catalyst to be synthesized and tested for the chemical and electrochemical conversion of CO₂ in Task 5.2. Moreover, Polito will deal with the choice of the microorganism and the process to be applied to test for the biochemical conversion of CO₂. The Dept. of Earth Sciences (UNITO) will deal with the carbon mineralization processes.

T5.1.2. Characterization of the composition of gases at the emitter.

The characterization of gases at the emitter will put the basis for the choice of the methods of carbon capture and conversion: this first step is necessary to avoid chemical competitors or interferers that will reduce the yield of the process. Moreover, concentration, water vapor content, operating temperature and pressure of the gases both at the emitter and at the conversion station will be determined to optimize the methods applied.

D) Deliverable D1.1

CO₂ capture:

Due to the huge volume of anthropogenic carbon dioxide (CO₂) production, CO₂ is deemed the largest greenhouse gas contributor to global warming. Since the Industrial Revolution era, the atmospheric concentration of this gas is growing exceeding the value of 400 ppm registered in recent years¹. To overcome this challenge many technologies have been developed in the area of post-combustion carbon dioxide capture in the last decades. Generally, various aspects such as selectivity and specificity towards carbon dioxide, a high working capacity, low cost, low regeneration requirements, long-term stability, fast kinetics, etc. affect the choice of the adsorbent materials together with process design and operating factors^{2,3}. The adsorption of post-combustion CO₂ with solvent scrubbing and membrane separation processes is a mature technology widely practised on a large scale for many years. However, these solutions undergo large energy costs associated with the high heat of adsorption and solvent regeneration⁴. Adsorption processes with selected materials capable of reversibly capturing CO₂ represent a more affordable approach since lower energy is required and CO₂ can be recovered to obtain consumer products⁵. A huge selection of adsorbents were studied for gas storage, such as amine-containing porous materials⁶, basic oxides^{7,8}, clays⁹, zeolites^{10,11}, carbons¹², silica¹³, and metal-organic frameworks (MOFs)¹⁴. Reflecting on a real-life application, typically, the composition of flue gases released by natural gas-fired power plants is 8–10% CO₂, 18–20% H₂O, 2–3% O₂, and 67–72% N₂¹⁵. The presence of water is a source of a wealth of effects on CO₂ adsorption. Indeed, an adsorption competition between water and CO₂ may occur when working with physical adsorbent (e.g., zeolites, activated carbons, MOFs), since, according to individual cases, water can strongly compete with CO₂ reducing drastically the uptakes^{16–18}.

Adsorbent type	Example	Adsorption temperature/ °C	CO ₂ adsorption capacity/ mmol g ⁻¹
Low temperature (< 200°C)	Carbon based	≤ 80	≤ 3.5
	Zeolite based	≤ 100	≤ 4.9
	MOF	≤ 100	≤ 4.5
	Alkali metal carbonates	≤ 120	≤ 9.4
	Amine based	≤ 60	≤ 5.5
Intermediate temperature (200°C – 400°C)	Layer Double Hydroxides	200-400	≤ 1.4
High temperature (< 400°C)	Calcium based	600-700	≤ 11.6
	Alkali ceramic based	500-600	≤ 6.5

Conversely, basic adsorbents (e.g., metal oxides, hydroxides, and carbonates) are able to react with CO₂ in a wide range of temperatures, proving noteworthy uptakes even in the presence of humidity, which can promote adsorption. Layered double hydroxides (LDHs) are inorganic crystalline materials composed of divalent and trivalent metal ions characterized by interesting features namely fast adsorption rate, ease of regeneration, and good thermal stability¹⁹. The impregnation of alkali metal salts would encourage the CO₂ adsorption performance of hydrotalcite. Moreover, the uptakes increase in the presence of water vapour compared to dry conditions, since under a humid gas the adsorption proceeds via the formation of transient hydroxylate species which then react with CO₂ to form carbonates. According to previous reports, the kinetics of CO₂ over these hydroxylates compounds is faster than that over the pure metal oxides facilitating the adsorption process^{8,19}.

Figure 1 Crystal structure of a typical layered double hydroxide (LDH) and illustration of the crystal structure, calcination of Mg–Al layered double hydroxide (LDH) and rehydration of the calcined LDH.

In this project we will synthesise LDH materials through the co-precipitation method²⁰. Typically, a salt solution of $Mg(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6 H_2O$ and $Al(NO_3)_3 \cdot 9 H_2O$ is added dropwise into a base solution of Na_2CO_3 . The pH of the precipitation solution is kept constant by the addition of NaOH solution. The resulting mixture is aged at room temperature for 24 h with continuous stirring and, subsequently, filtered and washed with deionized (DI) water until pH neutralization. Then the sample is dried at 100 °C in an oven. In order to overcome the adsorption capacities of the bare hydrotalcites, several doped LDH will be prepared with alkali metal salts solution of $NaNO_3$ and K_2CO_3 through an impregnation method¹⁹. The textural and physical-chemical features of the as-prepared materials will be carried out by the mean of powder X-ray diffractometry (XRD), N₂ physisorption at 77 K, TPDRO analysis, FESEM, FT-IR spectroscopy.

The CO₂ adsorption measurements will be performed employing an experimental set-up consisting of a reactor with a fixed adsorbent bed, a furnace, and a gas analyzer. In this system, the catalyst will be placed pelletized in a quartz U-shape reactor.

Figure 2 Laboratory setup for dynamic CO₂ adsorption-desorption experiments

Adsorption tests will carry out using a mixture of 5 vol.% of CO₂ in N₂ at 250°C in order to evaluate the material performances. The influence of moisture could be studied introducing a controlled degree of humidity in the inlet gas flow.

[Link to RMI](#): Furthermore, there are plans to use waste from the mining and construction industry as mining tailings or with segregation sludge.

Figure 3 example of A) high-temperature CO₂ adsorption and B) programmed desorption (TPD) experiment profiles.

CO₂ Conversion by thermochemistry:

As the greenhouse effect is significantly linked to CO₂ emissions, researchers are exploring sustainable approaches to reduce this environmental footprint. One of the promising methods involves capturing emitted CO₂ and recycling it in a closed-loop system. In this context, CO₂ chemical valorisation stands out as a potential solution by converting CO₂ into a wide array of valuable products, including essential chemicals and fuels.

A notable example of this process is the catalytic conversion of CO₂ and H₂ into methanol, a highly versatile component used in fuels, plastic production, paints, textile chemicals, and as a fundamental building block molecule. The potential economic benefits of such innovations have encouraged a growing interest in implementing this research at an industrial scale.

However, the practical application of CO₂ chemical valorisation faces a significant challenge: the low CO₂ conversion rate. This issue arises from limited catalyst selectivity and deactivation caused by the sintering of active metal particles. Overcoming these challenges is crucial to maximize the efficiency and feasibility of this environmentally friendly approach to CO₂

utilization. Continued research and development efforts are essential to enhance catalyst performance, improve selectivity, and mitigate deactivation phenomena.

Methanol (CH_3OH) is an important intermediate in chemical industry for many applications, as a chemical reactant or as a solvent. In addition, methanol can be used as a fuel increasing the use of renewable energies and reducing the carbon emissions (carbon capture and storage, CCS). Methanol is obtained by hydrogenation of carbon monoxide (CO) (1) or carbon dioxide (CO_2) (2), which are exothermic reactions. Moreover, reverse water gas shift (RWGS) reaction is a competing reaction, which produces CO through the CO_2 hydrogenation (3).

Hence, temperature control is a crucial feature of the reaction in order to maintain an adequate conversion, moderate the catalytic activity and avoid hot spots, deactivation phenomena or even run-away. The most common catalyst is Cu-based, promoted by ZnO , typically supported on a ceramic material, for instance alumina, zirconia or silica. This catalyst is remarkably selective towards methanol, which is not the thermodynamically favoured product of the reaction. Furthermore, by-products can be formed during the reaction, such as CO , hydrocarbons or higher alcohols. Moreover, the Cu-based catalyst is economically cheaper than the noble metals, such as platinum (Pt) or palladium (Pd)²¹.

A large amount of metal-based catalysts have been investigated for the thermocatalytic methanol synthesis from CO_2 ; however, the most common element for this type of reaction is the copper (Cu) coupled with a large number of promoters and supported on different materials. Figure 4 shows the most investigated metals for the preparation of the CO_2 hydrogenation to methanol catalysts.

Figure 4. Catalyst materials explored in literature for the CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol²¹

Our goal for this project is the development of optimized Cu-based catalysts for the conversion of CO₂ and H₂ into methanol by using a novel synthesis approach named 'exsolution'.^{22,23} Several different synthesis techniques (i.e., wet impregnation (WI), solution combustion synthesis (SCS), and gel-oxalate co-precipitation (OX)) have been already adopted and tested, with promising results obtained by varying the Cu atomic ratio. Specifically, the addition of different amounts of Cu boosted the catalytic activity of the samples by improving the methanol yield. However, due to the high mobility of Cu when infiltrated or present as secondary phase on oxide surfaces, these techniques have often showed undesired thermal agglomeration of Cu NPs at operating conditions, leading eventually to loss of activity. Therefore, the exsolution strategy, which sees the incorporation of the metal (i.e., Cu in this case) as ion into the 'host' structure during synthesis before its diffusion to the surface to form metallic nanoparticles when treated in controlled reduction conditions, will be employed to obtain Cu-metal NPs strongly anchored to the support, as previously shown for oxide systems²³. Moreover, the strain imposed by the NPs at the interface with the support by their unique "socketing" (i.e., anchorage), is expected to maximise the interactions between Cu and the support as well as stabilise the Cu NPs on the support surface, and hence to lead to an increased catalytic activity and stability compared to more-traditionally obtained catalysts.

Figure 5 Effect of the Cu particle size on the CO₂ conversion to methanol of Cu-CeO₂ binary oxide catalysts (Reaction conditions: 2.5 MPa, 20 NL·gcat⁻¹·h⁻¹, H₂/CO₂ = 3).

Preliminary explorative experiments have shown that exsolution of Cu NPs is possible from different structures, such as CeO₂ and ZnO/Al₂O₃, with promising characteristics for their testing in the CO₂ hydrogenation to MeOH reaction, such as good anchorage of the exsolved NPs to the support, homogeneous surface dispersion, and relatively small size (1-3 nm NPs).

CO₂ Conversion by electrochemistry

Rapid industrial and economic growth has significantly increased CO₂ emissions, causing global warming and environmental concerns²⁴. Carbon neutrality has emerged as an essential goal to combat the adverse effects of CO₂ emissions. From an energy perspective, CO₂ represents a readily available and economical carbon source that can be utilised to produce a variety of energy-intensive carbon-based fuels²⁵. The conversion of CO₂ into valuable chemicals and fuels is a promising solution²⁶. This approach offers a pathway towards sustainability and contributes to the overall reduction of greenhouse gas emissions. Nanostructured metal catalysts have been extensively studied for their potential in the electrocatalytic reduction of carbon dioxide. These catalysts' size, shape, and morphology have significantly influenced their performance in CO₂RR (CO₂ Reduction Reaction)²⁷. However, the current electrodes used for CO₂ reduction require further development to meet the criteria necessary for practical applications in CO₂RR. Hence, there is an urgent demand to create novel and highly efficient catalysts that can effectively facilitate the reduction of CO₂.

The primary objective of this deliverable is to provide a comprehensive overview of the materials to be tested for the electrocatalytic (EC) conversion of CO₂. After careful consideration and evaluation, bimetallic aerogels or xerogels made of Pd and Cu have been identified as potential materials because of their capabilities in CO₂RR. The following section will outline the description of each material and the rationale behind their selection.

Palladium and copper are both important metals that have been widely studied for their use in various electrochemical reactions, including the reduction of CO₂. Copper is an electrochemical

catalyst widely studied for its remarkable ability to reduce CO₂ to several hydrocarbons, acids, and alcohols^{28,29}. Nevertheless, Cu electrodes for CO₂ reduction have some limitations, including high overpotential, poor selectivity, and competition with hydrogen evolution. Researchers have attempted to address these issues by developing Cu complexes, nanoscale Cu, oxide-derived Cu, and alloys to improve selectivity and current density for CO₂ reduction to specific products³⁰. In contrast, Palladium-based systems have low overpotential for CO₂ reduction, but typically yield CO or HCOOH as major products, with low efficiency for producing alcohols³¹. It exhibits strong CO₂ adsorption capabilities, enabling increased CO₂ availability at the catalyst surface. Pd also demonstrates high stability and resistance to poisoning, allowing for prolonged catalytic activity. When combined as a bimetallic system, the synergistic effect of Pd and Cu in CO₂RR becomes evident^{32,33}. The integration of Pd into Cu-based catalysts enhances their catalytic performance and selectivity. The interaction between Pd and Cu species creates active sites with tailored electronic properties, promoting more efficient CO₂ activation and facilitating specific reaction pathways. The synergistic effect improves overall catalytic activity and selectivity towards desired CO₂RR products, making PdCu-based promising materials for CO₂ reduction applications.

The utilisation of bimetallic aerogels or xerogels composed of Pd and Cu leverages the strengths of both elements and offers a pathway for enhanced CO₂RR performance compared to individual metals alone. The aerogel form of these metals has gained significant attention in recent years because of their high surface area and excellent thermal and electrical conductivity^{34,35}. Recent developments in aerogel materials for electrocatalytic reduction of CO₂ have been demonstrated to yield promising results³⁶. The following paragraph aims to present the most effective materials and place our research within the current landscape of ongoing investigations.

Several works deal with Pd-based materials for their unique abovementioned properties. By taking advantage of the nanostructure engineering and new chemical reduction reaction, a novel, simple, eco-friendly, and surfactant-free procedure for fabricating self-assembled Pd aerogel was presented in the work of Hajnajafi and co-workers²⁷ using the spontaneous one-step gelation process for synthesis. In contrast with other methods, the advantages included being eco-friendly, simple, and having rapid synthesis. A palladium aerogel was prepared by reducing H₂PdCl₄ in ethanol utilising C₂H₅OH/NaOH as a green reductant agent in a short time for the first time, and in the following step, the palladium aerogel was obtained by supercritical drying. An extraordinary 3D nanonetwork of the Pd aerogel with large porosity was confirmed using several investigation methods. Due to the profuse open interconnected pores and large inner surface areas, the Pd aerogel showed highly boosted electrocatalytic activity toward the ethanol oxidation reaction and depicted much higher stability, durability, and mass activity in alkaline electrolyte than Pd/C. In a separate study by Abdinejad and co-workers³⁶, Sn-Pd bimetallic aerogels supported by carbon nanotubes were found to selectively electro-reduce CO₂ to formate under ambient conditions. The introduction of amino substituents as an

additional CO₂ capture site (Sn-Pd/CNT-NH₂) further enhanced the electrocatalytic activity, resulting in a current density of -39 mA cm^{-2} and 91% selectivity for formate at a potential of -0.4 V versus RHE. Moving from Pd to Cu-based materials, in 2021, Wang and co-workers³⁷ synthesised an Ag-Cu bimetallic aerogel by co-reducing Ag⁺ and Cu²⁺ precursors and freeze-drying the resulting material. The optimal composition obtained by controlling the equal molar ratio of Ag to Cu was Ag₈₈Cu₁₂. It demonstrated improved electrochemical stability, lower overpotential, higher selectivity, and current density compared to pure Ag aerogel. At a potential of -0.89 V versus RHE, the Faraday efficiency reached 89.40%, and the CO partial current density was -5.86 mA cm^{-2} . The unique properties of the metal aerogel, including its hydrophobic nature, hierarchical porous structure, and conductivity, as well as the presence of rich grain boundaries and the introduction of Cu, contributed to the enhanced performance of the Ag₈₈Cu₁₂ aerogel. Another use of copper, here not combined with noble metals, concerns a material based on Bi. In this study, different bimetallic Cu_xBi aerogel electrocatalysts with adjustable compositions were designed, which showed tunable selectivity for CO₂ reduction. The maximum Faradaic efficiency for CO and formate over Cu₁₀₀Bi and Cu₅Bi was 1.2 and 5.5 times higher than that of the pure Cu catalyst³⁸. Analysis using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy revealed that by varying the content of Bi in the catalysts, changes in the Cu(II)/Cu(I) ratios on the surface occur, which in turn regulated the hydrogenation capability of the reaction intermediates during CO₂ reduction. Finally, in a recent work³⁹, researchers developed a novel Pd₃Cu aerogel electrocatalyst through a mild reduction process using self-assembly and freeze-drying techniques. The resulting catalyst has a unique three-dimensional, "pearl-like" aerogel structure and exhibits exceptional performance due to its optimised chemical composition and structural features. Interestingly, Wu *et al.* utilised the same synthesis technique and selected the same metal catalysts as in this work, but for a different purpose - the search for an ORR catalyst. Finally, it is important to mention the work of Lu and co-workers⁴¹ about a Pd-Cu bimetallic aerogel used to selectively transform CO₂ to methanol via electrocatalytic reduction, obtaining a faradaic efficiency of around 80% at a very low overpotential.

Seeking to combine the capabilities of Cu and Pd and intrigued by the properties of aerogels, we have decided to synthesise Pd-Cu-based aerogels and xerogels. These materials have been chosen for their potential in CO₂ electrocatalytic reduction, specifically targeting the production of green H₂ and C-based products. The materials will undergo comprehensive characterisation using techniques such as transmission electron microscopy (TEM), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), N₂ physisorption analysis, and X-ray diffraction (XRD). These analytical methods will provide valuable insights into the morphology, composition, surface chemistry, porosity, and crystal structure of the synthesised Pd-Cu-based aerogels and xerogels, facilitating a thorough understanding of their properties and optimising their catalytic performance. The performance of the synthesised materials will be carried out in lab-scale EC systems, including H-type and gas diffusion electrode (GDE) cells, to investigate their efficacy to boost the

electrochemical reduction of CO₂. The aim is to harness the unique properties of Pd and Cu, combined with the advantageous characteristics of aerogels, to enhance the selectivity and efficiency of CO₂ conversion processes.

CO₂ Conversion by photochemistry

Solvated electrons are transient species long known but actually considered as synthesis intermediates only in recent years. Solvated electrons have a sufficiently high standard reduction potential to reduce CO₂⁴².

Many semiconductors, such as titanium dioxide, are capable of producing solvated electrons, but the problem lies in their rapid recombination to return the semiconductor to its ground state. Their reactivity depends greatly on their speed of exiting the solvation sphere of the species that generated them. Many inorganic anions are capable of producing solvated electrons and can lead to the reduction of bicarbonate to organic acids when irradiated with UVC (254 nm)⁴³.

In a more general context, ionizing radiation serves as a source of solvated electrons, just as atmospheric plasmas can produce them on the surface of a liquid in contact with the plasma^{44,45,46}.

Even photons with longer wavelengths can produce solvated electrons when surface plasmon resonance (SPR) is utilized. Among the various examples in the literature, it is interesting to mention the formation of solvated electrons through SPR on non-noble metals (e.g., Al) with a wavelength of 396 nm (violet light). Clearly, the production of solvated electrons through SPR on noble metals like gold is widely described in the literature, although few examples apply to the reduction of carbon dioxide^{47,48}.

Figure 6 *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2022, 144, 44, 20183–20189

Figure 7 Schematic illustration of the role of CuPd co-catalyst in capturing CO₂ molecules. Plasmonic catalysis usually takes place very close to the catalyst surface ⁴⁸

Of recent particular interest is the preparation and use of nanoparticles supported on carbonaceous materials ⁴⁹.

Figure 8 hybrid plasmonic photocatalyst ⁴⁹

When considering visible light, sulfonated iridium complexes can lead to the formation of solvated electrons upon irradiation with visible light. Iridium complexes are also responsible for the photoreduction of CO₂ using visible light (480 nm, quantum yield of 0.13), with the possibility of using water as a solvent ⁵⁰.

Several inorganic anions have been tested under UV irradiation, leading to the formation of carboxylic acids. Among these, some result in the formation of bicarboxylic acids, which are of interest for synthetic applications. We have also studied the photoionization yield of various aromatic anionic dyes and will proceed with experiments using C¹³-labeled bicarbonate.

Simultaneously, we are utilizing laser diode irradiation at 800, 900, and 405 nm (diodes with high energy efficiency) on pyrolytic carbons decorated with metallic nanoparticles.

CO₂ Conversion by biochemistry

Microalgae biomass production

Over the last century, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, such as CO₂, continued to increase due to anthropogenic activities, significantly contributing to climate change^{51,52}. Therefore, interest is rising to develop new faster, greener, and possibly bio-based Carbon Capture and Utilization (CCU) technologies that can effectively reduce carbon dioxide emissions and minimize the impact on the environment of several industrial processes⁵². In this context, microalgal carbon bio-fixation is a promising candidate to be one of the most effective CO₂ re-utilization techniques⁵³, which allows the carbon incorporation into a variety of Value-Added Products (VAPs). Thus, the microalgal biomass have many applications in different industrial sectors, such as health care, cosmetic, food, feed, and fuel⁵⁴. Even more, microalgae have also faster growth rates compared to that of higher plants and their cultivation does not compete with arable land⁵⁵. The main goal of industrial scale microalgae cultivation is to enhance the CO₂ fixation through an appropriate mixing, gas transfer and culture condition (pH, temperature, light intensity, and wavelength composition). The two main techniques to cultivate microalgae are open ponds and closed systems called Photobioreactors (PBRs). Microalgae biomass production using open ponds presents several issues due to the incurrence of culture contaminations, photoperiodic changes, and general difficult cultivation condition control (temperature, pH, % CO₂ dissolved in the medium, mass transfer coefficient among others). For these reasons, PBRs are currently under investigation to solve open systems main problems, providing a new tool to produce a higher value microalgal biomass with a high efficiency in CO₂ remediation. PBRs design is crucial to optimize growth and CO₂ fixation performances with changes in the system hydrodynamics to achieve a better CO₂ dissolution, besides to improve energy consumption efficiency by light intensity and spectrum composition manipulation⁵⁶.

Figure 9 schematic representation of the PBR used in this work; 1) Probes holder; 2) Tank; 3) Hydraulic pump; 4) CO₂ inlet; 5) PLC; 6) LEDs Power supply; 7) Polycarbonate hydraulic panel; 8) PMMA Light Guide; 9) Probes digital signal.

In this initial part of the project an own made experimental pilot-scale pressurized planar PBR (Fig. 9) has been used and equipped to investigate the CO₂ bio-fixation efficiencies of two commercially promising species, the green microalga *Acutodesmus obliquus* and the red extremophile microalga *Galdieria sulphuraria*. To do so, fundamental growth parameters such as temperature, light intensity, and pH were finely adjusted according to the needs of the two microalgae species. Furthermore, the CO₂ injection system of the PBR was designed to precisely calibrate CO₂ in-flow and its quantification. A carbon mass balance based on produced biomass and its elemental composition was then used to evaluate the CO₂ bio-fixation efficiencies of the two microalgae species. The system allows us to unpack the entire visible spectrum with the use of 10 LEDs evenly distributed along the structure. The analysis of the incident light distribution along the entire surface of the flat panels can be also evaluated and managed. The efficiency of the system will be tested by carrying out batch tests with two commercially relevant microalgae, phylogenetically distant and with different pigment composition and abiotic conditions requirements. For each microalga, a specific light spectrum composition will be applied based on the oxygen evolution response as a performance indicator of photosynthesis from the cells exposed to the different wavelengths. The promising biomass yields obtained with both species reflect the potential and versatility of the PBR used. The possibility of monitoring all growth parameters, as well as the tuning of light intensity and quality, make this system an excellent platform for the study and growth at a semi-pilot scale of several targeted algae or desired products. Various considerations and suggestions, especially related to the system's fluid dynamics, are going to be tested in the future months, and will help to further improve the proposed technology and to evaluate its possible use in an industrial scenario, in which the application of energy-efficient technologies is nowadays a priority.

Based on preliminary screening and on previous work we selected the already cited microalgae strains that have the following characteristics:

- *Acutodesmus* is a family of green algae which usually can be found in freshwater sources as lakes or rivers. Spherical shaped, this organism can grow on a wide variety of environmental conditions with pH ranging from 6.5 to 9 and temperatures going from 10 to 40 °C depending on the species. *Acutodesmus* cell can accumulate high amount of lipids and carbohydrates, reaching percentage as 60% of the total dry weight for lipids and 50% of it for carbohydrates. Because of this, *Acutodesmus* is a viable candidate for bio-diesel and bio-ethanol production. Higher level of carbon dioxide were instead favourable for the accumulation of lipids and polyunsaturated fatty acids. For what concern *Acutodesmus* food potential, Vendruscolo et al. (2022) evaluated the composition in terms of proteins, pigments and lipids resulting from being grown at different CO₂ concentration. Results of this experiment showed that *A. obliquus* protein content was 57.8 and 57.2 % of the total mass for CO₂ concentration of 5 and 10%. An increase of CO₂ caused slightly decrease of protein content while increased total lipids. The production peak of carotenoids was obtained at 3% CO₂, even if at 5 and 10% the production was still significant. Carotenoids content was 25.3 ± 0.5, 22.7 ± 0.1 and 18.1 ± 1.0 mg g⁻¹ at respectively 3, 5 and 10% CO₂. A further increase in CO₂ caused strong decrease in carotenoid production. According to the authors of this study, treatment with CO₂ from 3 to 10% produced a biomass with a high potential for application in food and food integration.

- *Galdieria sulphuraria* is a poly-extremophile red microalga able to tolerate low pH (as low as 0.2), high temperature (up to 57 °C) and high osmotic pressure (up to 400 g L⁻¹ of sugar and 2–3 M of salt). Due to some peculiar features, *G. sulphuraria* is now considered a promising biotechnological platform for several applications, from pharmaceutical to cosmetics and nutraceutical applications:

- C-phycoyanin (C-PC) content of 10% w/w, like the C-PC content commonly reported in *Arthrospira platensis* (Spirulina). Nevertheless, *Galdieria*'s extracted C-PC has shown greater stability at low pH and at high temperature, increasing the possible industrial applications of this pigment.
- Protein content up to an impressive 72% of total biomass dry weight.
- Its protein quality in terms of amino acid composition is a core marker for nutritional value, being rich of sulfur-containing amino acids.
- While *Spirulina* has been consumed for centuries and its consumption is approved and considered safe worldwide, *G. sulphuraria* has no previous history of use in feed or foods. Recent studies indicated that *G. sulphuraria* could be safe as food ingredient or supplements, and its application as novel food is currently under review by the European Food Safety Authority.

The first aim of the project will be to test our PBR with both strains, and to feed the culture medium with pure CO₂ adjusting the flow according to the culture metabolism and aiming to an efficiency in terms of carbon dioxide bio fixation higher than 90%.

CO₂ Conversion by bio-hybrid system

This technology aims to enhance efficiency and specificity of the electrochemical reduction of carbon dioxide (CO₂) to formic acid, a high-energy-density liquid compound used for fuel production as well as by employing recombinant Clostridial oxygen-tolerant and tungsten dependent Formate Dehydrogenase (FDH) with semiconductor and nanostructured electrodes and photoactivated nanomaterials. The study involves the immobilization of FDH on the electrode surface and optimizing its catalytic performance for formate production. By systematically varying operational conditions and leveraging advanced nanomaterials, we seek to maximize CO₂ conversion efficiency and long-term stability of the bio-hybrid system, while formate production selectivity is already provided by the biocatalyst.

Excellency examples are provided on this bio-hybrid approach by the group of Erwin Reisner at Cambridge University (UK) but on different FDHs and materials⁵⁷. Here we aim at selecting and producing more robust and durable enzymes.

Figure 10 Formate Dehydrogenase

The gene encoding Clostridial oxygen-tolerant metal dependent FDH⁵⁸ is cloned and inserted into an expression vector for recombinant protein production in *Escherichia coli* hosts. The transformed *E. coli* cells are grown in a suitable culture medium to induce FDH expression. We have already selected and ordered 4 different enzymes form various clostridial strains, yet unexploited, that have the potential oxygen tolerance required for technological applications. The recombinant FDH is extracted and purified using chromatographic techniques, ensuring high enzyme yield and purity. This is a consolidated expertise of the group and the expression yields are already in the range of 10-120 mg/l of culture.

The enzyme's oxygen tolerance is validated through oxygen sensitivity tests. The possibility of further enhancement of the biocatalyst's performance will be tested by inserting a

selenocysteine which is expected to maximize the turnover frequency of the reaction of CO₂ reduction⁵⁹.

Different metal oxides nanomaterials, including photo-activated semiconductors and nanostructured electrodes will be available for interfacing with the FDH enzyme. Characterization using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and X-ray diffraction (XRD) is conducted to confirm nanomaterial properties and bio-hybrid structure. This will also be analyzed via ATR FTIR. The extracted FDH is covalently or physically immobilized onto the electrode surface. The optimal FDH loading and immobilization method are determined through systematic experimentation.

Electrochemical CO₂ reduction experiments are conducted using the FDH- modified electrodes in a custom-built electrochemical cell. The electrocatalytic performance is monitored by measuring current density, faradaic efficiency, and formate production. Preliminary data were collected on TiO₂ providing gaseous CO₂ which seems to be confirmed as the actual substrate instead of HCO₃⁻ ⁶⁰.

The impact of key operational parameters, including pH, temperature, applied potential and light wavelength and intensity, on CO₂ conversion efficiency and formate yield (quantitated by HPLC analysis of formate) will be studied to identify the optimal conditions.

The successful recombinant expression of Clostridial oxygen-tolerant FDH in *E. coli*, coupled with the efficient immobilization on nanostructured materials and electrodes, is anticipated to result in enhanced CO₂ conversion and formate production stable in time. The synergistic interaction between the biocatalyst and nanomaterials is expected to significantly outperform conventional electrocatalysts. This innovative approach represents a promising avenue for sustainable CO₂ utilization and formate production.

The application of recombinant tungsten-dependent Clostridial oxygen-tolerant FDH in *E. coli* for enhanced CO₂ conversion with semiconducting nanomaterials holds great potential for sustainable energy generation and carbon capture. Through a meticulous investigation of operational parameters and advanced nanomaterials, this project seeks to contribute to the advancement of CO₂ conversion technologies. The successful implementation of this innovative approach may have far-reaching implications in combating climate change and promoting a greener and more sustainable future.

Characterization of the composition of gases at the emitter:

We conducted a comprehensive review of existing literature to identify the composition of gases suitable for our capture and conversion tests. The examination of the literature enabled us to select the most appropriate gas mixtures for our experiments, ensuring that we are building upon the established practices in the energy production sector to develop efficient and effective solutions for capture and conversion processes.

Using power plants as a reference to simulate gas emissions is motivated by several reasons:

- Power plants represent one of the major sectors responsible for greenhouse gas emissions and air pollutants. Therefore, using them as a reference provides a realistic simulation of real emission sources. Flue gases resulting from the combustion of fossil fuels are among the major sources of carbon dioxide (CO₂) and other greenhouse gases emitted into the atmosphere.
- Power plants often provide detailed data on their emissions, including the composition of emitted gases. This data is valuable for research and development of capture and conversion technologies.
- Improving efficiency and reducing emissions from Power plants is crucial for mitigating climate change. Simulating emissions from these plants allows for the development of sustainable solutions for the energy sector.
- Gas capture and conversion technologies need to be implemented on an industrial scale to have a significant impact. Knowledge gained from power plants can be directly applied in such contexts.

The gas compositions we draw inspiration from for adsorption and conversion tests typically include the following components: 5–14% CO₂, 6–20% H₂O, 2–10% O₂, and 67–76% N₂⁶¹⁻⁶³. The tests will typically be conducted using only CO₂ (5-10%) and N₂ under dry conditions, with a maximum of 10% H₂O under wet conditions. We exclude the presence of oxygen from our lines to avoid overly complicating gas dilution calculations.

E) Milestone

M5.1 At least one material to be tested for each conversion process and also microorganism for the biochemical process will be selected.

At the end of this deliverable, the following technologies have been selected for testing:

- **CO₂ capture:** Layered double hydroxides (LDHs)
- **Chemical conversion:** Optimized Cu-based catalysts synthesized by a novel approach named 'exsolution'
- **Electrochemical conversion:** Pd-Cu-based aerogels and xerogels
- **Photochemical conversion:** Hybrid plasmonic photocatalyst
- **Biochemical conversion:** microalga (*Acutodesmus* and *Galdieria sulphuraria*)
- **Bio-hybrid conversion:** recombinant tungsten-dependent Clostridial oxygen-tolerant FDH in *E. coli* for enhanced CO₂ conversion with semiconducting nanomaterials

The goals of the milestone have therefore been fully achieved.

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